

YOU ARE THE PRIDE OF THE NATION, MY MOTHER TONGUE

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Annotation: In this article, it is emphasized that the mother tongue is one of the rich languages, it is the pride and honor of the nation. It was mentioned that the national language and national pride should be brought up in the spirit of patriotism, loyalty to national traditions and values of the young generation.

The role of the mother tongue is important in the spiritual development of a person, in the cultural and educational development of his society. Our mother tongue is another spirit that unites peoples, educates them, preserves customs, traditions and cultures, ensures that they are passed from generation to generation, and makes everyone feel the sign of love in their hearts. A person understands the concept of Motherland for the first time in his mother tongue, and in this language he hears the God who gives peace and tranquility to his heart. That is probably why the concepts of language, nation, and Motherland are always side by side. In fact, the language clearly expresses the culture and spirituality of a nation, its ancient history, and a set of traditions specific to that nation. If the language is alive, the nation will live. The history of the Uzbek language is closely connected with the centuries-old past, dreams, aspirations, pains, and victories of our people. Our

ancestors spoke to the world through our mother tongue. He created great scientific discoveries and artistic masterpieces in this language. To find out how many thousands of years of history the Uzbek language has, you should read the works of Mahmud Kashgari, Yusuf Khos Hajib. Only then will you be sure once again that our unique language is one of the oldest languages. And Hazrat Navoi encouraged us to be proud of our mother tongue with the phrase “Pay attention to the language - pay attention to the hand” and finished “Khamsa” in this language and raised it to the heights.

One of our contemporary linguists said: “Navoi’s work is an endless ocean for learning our language”. Alisher Navoi’s great goal was to show the world the expressive possibilities of the Turkish language and its artistic features. When we read the works of our great ancestor, we understand how deep the roots of the Uzbek language are, how wide and rich the possibilities of this language are. After Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur undertook to raise our language to the level of classical literary languages. Shah and poet Babur Mirza realized the need to create a new alphabet that would fully express the rich tones and sounds of the Turkish language and created “Hatti Baburiy”. Boborahim Mashrab, Muhammad Reza Ogahi, Muqimi, Furqat, Cholpon, Fitrat, Abdulla Kadiri, Gafur Ghulam, Abdulla Oripov, Oybek, Olmas Umarbekov, Abdulla Qahhor, Erkin Vahidov, Rauf Parpi a number of representatives of Uzbek literature raised the status of our language and nation with their works. Also, language is the first sign of a nation. Its development is closely related to the development of this nation. Language is, first of all, a certificate of national independence.

The status of the state language was also legally strengthened in our main dictionary. In this way, the Uzbek language became one of the sacred symbols protected by law. The adoption of the law on the state language further raised the status of our language in society and created the ground for further development of our language. In the decree of the President of October 21, 2019 “On measures to

fundamentally increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as a state language”, important tasks for further increasing the status of our native language were defined. According to the decree, the preparation of drafts of normative legal documents on the development of the state language, the development of the program and “Roadmaps” for the development of the state language, the coordination of work on the celebration of the “Uzbek language holiday”, scientifically based new Implementation of a number of tasks, such as the introduction of the terms z and This document brought the development of our language, its preservation and development to a new stage in our country. At the same time, as we have witnessed, significant work is being done in our country to implement the tasks envisaged by this document.

Mother tongue is a source of good qualities and high feelings. It occupies a unique place in human development. Because our mothers tell us alla in this language, they instill the knowledge and concepts necessary for human life through the medium of language into our consciousness, our manners and character are formed on the basis of the instructions and advice given through the language. In particular, the formation of human thinking is directly related to language. Because when we think about the properties of something, we understand its specific aspects, relying on concepts, thoughts and imaginations, each of which is expressed in a specific word. In the 80s of the last century, the great scholar Alikhontora Soguni wrote in his book “The Sorrow of Turkistan”: “A person should not lose three things in order not to forget his identity: his homeland, his religion and his language. We lost our country. We also lost our religion. Now, if we forget our language, who will we be?” These questions are the truth. Our sacred language, which we honored during the time of the former union, existed on paper, but in practice it did not exist. For many years, we lived according to our language with which our great ancestors communicated and created comprehensive historical works. We couldn’t express our feelings through language. We had to speak the

language of the oppressed, sing songs, and even shout “I have two mothers...”.

The Republic of Uzbekistan’s desire for independence, the first bold step towards independence, began with the granting of the status of the State language to the Uzbek language. A legal basis was created for the preservation, restoration, preservation and promotion of our national language, which has been stifled and devalued for many years before independence was declared. Today, born together with the nation, passing through all the quiet and silent periods of the glorious history together with the nation, sharing the pains and joys of the nation, the Motherland is boundless and sacred, dignified and virtuous like a mother, close like a soul. and the status of our dear Uzbek language is increasing even more. In fact, the Uzbek language has bravely followed the path of many thousand years of historical development to this day. The scientific, literary, spiritual and educational resources created from the inscriptions on the Orhun-Enasoy monuments to the present period are about the tendencies of the formation and development of the Uzbek language, literary expression, layers of meaning, and vocabulary. can give detailed and reasonable information. Beginning with rare examples of folklore, records on ancient inscriptions, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Mahmud Kashgari, Ahmad Yassavi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Lutfi, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Mashrab, Ogahi, Furqat, Uvaisi, Nadira, Behbudi, The legacy of creative thinkers such as Fitrat, Qadiri, Cholpon, Usman Nasir is one of the important sources in this regard. In addition, representatives of the next generation, representatives of the enlightenment, literature of the 20th-21st centuries, linguists, scholars of literature, with their artistic, creative, scientific activities, enrich the Uzbek language with their literary, spiritual and educational and has been making a significant contribution to its growth and development.

Only through this national language can we understand the heritage of our ancestors, life stories of the distant and recent past, the historical foundations of our statehood, our national values and traditions, and ensure that they are passed on to

the next generation. For this reason, the Uzbek language has a high status as a “symbol of national identity and independent statehood, a great value” of the Uzbek people. In the work of our first president, Islam Karimov: “...self-awareness, the expression of national consciousness and thinking, the spiritual-spiritual connection between generations is manifested through language. with the unique charm of his tongue. The mother tongue is the soul of the nation,” it was noted. Abdulla Avloni, our enlightener and outstanding writer, said: Language and literature are the mirror of every nation’s existence in the world. How right he was when he expressed his clear and deep thoughts, “To lose the national language is to lose the soul of the nation.” Abdulla Awlani’s opposition to any attempts and contradictory actions aimed at destroying the native language and literature, mixing it with other languages, changing its content, and ultimately, the supremacy of one language over another, and the destruction of the spirit of the language, is evident in the following Purmana words.

Language is a mirror of the nation, destiny, interest, symbol of statehood. To protect, preserve, promote, polish, and stabilize it is the human task and moral duty of every citizen of this country and representatives of this nation. Among the languages of the world, the Uzbek language has acquired a special dignity and charm with its expressive edges, expressiveness, and literary laws, and has fascinated the people of knowledge and the leaders of enlightenment. It makes us all proud. In our country, which is boldly moving from national recovery to national growth, special attention was paid to the development of our mother tongue, and high respect was shown. In fact, the Uzbek language and culture will develop further in the world civilization, it will rise to the level of an international language that can captivate the people of the world with its beauty, charm, and pronunciation like melodious music. sincerely respect. We young people, who are the main promoters and defenders of the state language, invite all our compatriots and compatriots to unite, become partners and like-minded people in the development

of the Uzbek language. After all, strength is in unity, progress is in unity, progress is in unity, prosperity is in cooperation.

Alisher Navoi, the Sultan of the word property, said, “The lock of the heart is the lock of the heart, and the key of the heart is the word, that is, the key to the treasure of the human heart is the word”. The centuries-old rich history of our people, the ancient and colorful culture was formed under the influence of the Uzbek language. Our great poet Alisher Navoi created priceless works in this language and amazed the world. In this language, our mother tongue sounds and is developing. Language is a means of communication between people and is an invaluable gift of the creator to man. Language is one of the main characteristics that distinguish nations from nations. The language of every nation in the world is its priceless wealth, pride, and salvation. As long as there is a nation, its language will live, and as long as its language lives, that nation will have its prestige and prestige among other nations. Every nation has its own language. Language is the mirror of every nation, its true reflection. As long as there is a language, the nation is alive. It is not for nothing that language is compared to a mother, a person cannot live without seeing his mother, without feeling her pure love and affection.

As a proof of this opinion, we can cite the speech given by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the occasion of the 30th anniversary of the granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language: “If anyone wants to feel the grace, charm and influence of the Uzbek language, and its limitless possibilities, the gods of our mothers, a thousand let him hear our annual epics, our immortal statuses, listen to the magical songs of our bakhshi and hafiz”. National language is the main source of communication of peoples and nations. Language unites peoples, educates, preserves customs, traditions and cultures, ensures their transmission from generation to generation. Language is a symbol of the country, it is a valuable property. If the culture of the language is not followed, the national culture will be tarnished. To love the language is equal to

honoring it, loving the nation and appreciating it. The lifestyle, customs, and culture of any nation find expression in its language. It is not for nothing that they say that the language is the mirror of the nation. Our nation's centuries-old rich history, ancient and rich culture was formed under the influence of the Uzbek language - our mother tongue. It is the civic duty of all of us to educate in the spirit of devotion to values, to fully apply the state language to life. Language, nation, state... These three concepts cannot be imagined separately from each other. Everyone speaks in his native language, thinks in his native language, feels in his native language, dreams in his native language...

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